

The Role of Social Studies Education in Youth Skills Acquisition and Development in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

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Abstract

This study was focused on the role of Social Studies Education in youth skills acquisition and development in Upper Basic schools in Delta State. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population consist of 49,796 Upper Basic 2 students in public secondary schools in Delta State. The sample comprises 250 Upper Basic 2 students selected through stratified sampling technique across the UBE schools in Delta State. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire designed to gather data from Upper Basic 2 students on the role of Social Studies in youth skills acquisition and development. It assessed students' views on skill acquisition, critical thinking, and problem-solving. The questionnaire included sections on demographics and specific skill domains, using a 4-Likert- scale for responses. Data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to summarize responses and chi-square analysis to test hypotheses. The result showed that Social Studies education significantly enhances youth skills acquisition among students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State, Social Studies education has a significant impact on the development of critical thinking skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State; and Social Studies education has a significant impact on the development of problem-solving skills among students in upper basic schools in Delta State. It was recommended that enhancing the Social Studies curriculum with skill-based learning, interactive teaching methods, and practical applications will improve students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Keywords: Social Studies, youth skills acquisition, skill development, critical thinking, problem-solving

Introduction

Social Studies Education serves as an essential component of the educational curriculum, designed to prepare students for responsible citizenship and holistic development (Olokooba & Lawal, 2024). It integrates various disciplines such as history, geography, political science, and economics to instill knowledge, skills, and values essential for societal progress (Yusuf, 2024). Scholars emphasize that Social Studies is not only about knowledge acquisition but also about skill development, particularly in areas like critical thinking, problem-solving, and civic participation (Muhammad, 2024).

Youth skills acquisition is a critical objective of modern education systems, particularly in developing nations where unemployment and lack of entrepreneurial skills remain challenges (Njoku, 2023). Social Studies plays a pivotal role in equipping students with practical skills necessary for economic self-sufficiency and community development (Bishara & Gidado, 2024). Studies suggest that through Social Studies education, students develop essential communication, collaboration, and leadership skills that are transferable to various career paths (Ruto et.al, 2023). The interactive nature of Social Studies seems to foster hands-on learning experiences that promote skills acquisition.

Critical thinking is an essential 21st-century skill that enables students to analyze situations, evaluate evidence, and make informed decisions (Thornhill-Miller et.al, 2023). Social Studies education, with its emphasis on inquiry-based learning could stimulate students' ability to think critically about social issues. Research has shown that students exposed to Social Studies curricula that incorporate debates, case studies, and problem-based learning exhibit higher levels of critical thinking (Bayram & Deveci, 2022).). In addition, the use of primary and secondary sources in Social Studies may tend to foster analytical thinking and perspective-taking, which are crucial in decision-making. Problem-solving skills could enable students to address real-world issues using logical reasoning and creative solutions. Social Studies education plays a significant role in developing problem-solving abilities by encouraging students to assess societal challenges, propose solutions, and evaluate outcomes (Ifegbesan, 2023). Social Studies activities such as role-playing, simulations, and project-based assignments may help students cultivate a problem-solving

mindset. Moreover, exposure to historical case studies could also equip students with the ability to draw lessons from past events to solve contemporary problems.

Several educational theories tend to support the role of Social Studies education in youth skills development. Constructivist theories, particularly those proposed by Piaget and Vygotsky, argue that active engagement in learning fosters deeper understanding and skill acquisition (Wibowo, et.al, 2025). Additionally, Dewey's theory of education underscores the role of Social Studies in preparing students for participatory citizenship through reflective thinking (Martinelle et.al, 2024).

Numerous empirical studies highlight the significance of Social Studies in skill development among students. Obro et.al (2021), who studied effective social studies pedagogy, effect of simulation games and brainstorming strategies on students' learning outcome revealed that students who engaged in Social Studies activities demonstrated improved decision-making skills. Similarly, research by Ogundele (2021) found that Social Studies-based interventions enhanced students' ability to analyze and respond to societal issues critically. Achor et.al (2017) in their study on teacher preparation in Social Studies curriculum for promoting entrepreneurship education at Upper Basic Education level in Benue State revealed that making skill acquisition a core course in Social Studies curriculum will create awareness about its importance to teenagers especially in developing a spirit of self-reliance and reduction of youth unemployment to a very high extent in Nigeria.

Despite its significance, several challenges hinder the effective implementation of Social Studies education for skills development. These include inadequate instructional materials, lack of trained educators, and an overemphasis on rote memorization rather than practical application (Adeyemi & Onigiobi, 2020). Furthermore, curriculum rigidity and assessment methods that focus primarily on factual recall rather than skill demonstration limit the potential impact of Social Studies education (Yaw, 2024). Addressing these challenges may require policy reforms, teacher training, and the integration of technology to enhance interactive learning experiences.

Given the critical role of Social Studies education in youth skills development, policymakers must prioritize curriculum reforms that emphasize competency-based learning and teachers should be equipped with innovative pedagogical strategies that promote active learning and critical

engagement (Tumuheise et.al, 2023). Additionally, schools may need to incorporate digital tools and experiential learning opportunities to enhance students' acquisition of critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Social Studies education serves as a vital tool for equipping students with essential life skills, including youth skills acquisition, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. To maximize its benefits, educational stakeholders must address existing challenges and adopt progressive teaching methodologies that align with global best practices in skill development.

Statement of Problem

Social Studies education is widely acknowledged for its potential role in fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and civic engagement among students. However, the extent to which it contributes to youth skills acquisition—particularly in areas such as communication, collaboration, and digital literacy—remains insufficiently explored, especially within the context of upper basic schools in Delta State, Nigeria. Although the curriculum is intended to equip learners with relevant 21st-century competencies, it is unclear whether these objectives are being effectively achieved in practice. This uncertainty is especially relevant in light of ongoing concerns about youth unemployment and underemployment in Nigeria, which are often linked to gaps in practical and transferable skills among school leavers.

Despite policy emphasis on skills-based education, existing literature offers limited empirical insight into how Social Studies is implemented in a way that supports youth skills development at the upper basic level. In addition, varying instructional methods, teacher preparedness, and resource availability may influence the subject's effectiveness in this regard. These unresolved issues underscore the need for a deeper examination of how Social Studies education is contributing—or failing to contribute—to equipping students with the skills necessary for navigating both academic and real-life challenges. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the role of Social Studies education in youth skills acquisition and development, with a view to generating evidence-based recommendations for curriculum improvement, teacher training, and policy reform.

Objectives of the Study

1. examine the extent to which Social Studies education enhances youth skills acquisition among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.
2. assess the impact of Social Studies education on the development of critical thinking skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.
3. assess the impact of Social Studies education on the development of problem-solving skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does Social Studies education enhance youth skills acquisition among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?
2. What impact does Social Studies education have on the development of critical thinking skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?
3. What impact does Social Studies education have on the development of problem-solving skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Hypotheses

1. Social Studies education does not significantly enhance youth skills acquisition among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.
2. Social Studies education has no significant impact on the development of critical thinking skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?
3. Social Studies education has no significant impact on the development of problem-solving skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This design was chosen because it allows for the collection of quantitative data from a representative sample to describe the existing conditions, opinions, and attitudes regarding the role of Social Studies education in youth skills acquisition and development in upper basic schools in Delta State. The population for this study comprised all Upper Basic 2 students in public secondary schools in Delta State, totaling 49,796

students enrolled in 2023/2024. This population was selected because Upper Basic 2 students have had sufficient exposure to the Social Studies curriculum and can provide relevant insights into its impact on skills acquisition and development. A sample of 250 Upper Basic 2 students was selected using a stratified sampling technique. This technique ensured that students were drawn proportionally from different schools across Delta State, representing the diverse educational settings within the region. The selection process was designed to capture a balanced representation of students from urban and rural schools.

The primary instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to assess students' perceptions of the role of Social Studies education in youth skills acquisition, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills development. It comprised of closed-ended questions rated on a 4-point Likert scale: Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), Very Low Extent (1), and Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1).

To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, it was subjected to expert review. Three experts in Social Studies education and educational measurement and evaluation reviewed the instrument for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives. Their feedback was used to refine the questionnaire, ensuring that it effectively captured the constructs being measured. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined through a pilot study involving 30 students from schools that were not part of the main study. The internal consistency of the instrument was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient. The obtained reliability coefficient of **0.82** indicated a high level of reliability, confirming that the questionnaire items consistently measured the intended constructs.

Data collection was carried out through direct administration of the questionnaire to the selected respondents. The researcher, along with trained research assistants, distributed and retrieved the completed questionnaires to ensure a high response rate and accuracy in data collection. The collected data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to summarize and interpret the responses to the research questions. Inferential statistics, specifically chi-square analysis, were employed to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The chi-square test determined whether significant

relationships existed between Social Studies education and youth skills acquisition, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills development

Results

This section presented the findings based on responses gathered through a structured questionnaire designed to assess students' perceptions of the role of Social Studies education in youth skills acquisition, critical thinking, and problem-solving skill development. The questionnaire consisted of items grouped under each research question and was measured using a 4-point Likert scale. Responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics—mean and standard deviation—to determine the extent of agreement among students. The interpretation is based on the cumulative mean scores, where a higher mean reflects stronger agreement with each construct.

Research question 1: To what extent does Social Studies education enhance youth skills acquisition among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Table 1: Social Studies and Youth skills acquisition

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Decision
1	To what extent has Social Studies education improved your ability to work effectively in a team?	3.53	0.70	Agreed
2	To what extent has the Social Studies curriculum enhanced your understanding of economic principles applicable to daily life?	3.42	0.66	Agreed
3	To what extent have you developed better decision-making skills through Social Studies education?	3.61	0.74	Agreed
4	To what extent have Social Studies lessons increased your awareness of cultural diversity and its importance?	3.50	0.68	Agreed
5	To what extent has Social Studies equipped you with skills to analyze societal issues critically?	3.54	0.71	Agreed
6	To what extent do you feel more prepared to participate in community development activities due to your Social Studies education?	3.40	0.64	Agreed

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Decision
7	To what extent has Social Studies taught you how to effectively communicate your ideas and opinions?	3.51	0.69	Agreed
Cumulative Mean		3.50		Agreed

The cumulative mean score of **3.50** suggests a general agreement that Social Studies education significantly enhances youth skills acquisition. The low standard deviations (ranging from 0.64 to 0.74) indicate consistency in students' responses. Thus, the findings affirm that Social Studies education in upper basic schools in Delta State plays a crucial role in equipping students with essential life skills, including teamwork, decision-making, critical thinking, economic literacy, cultural awareness, and communication skills, all of which contribute to their overall development and readiness for societal participation.

Research question 2: What impact does Social Studies education have on the development of critical thinking skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Social Studies and development of critical thinking

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Decision
1	Social Studies education helps students develop critical thinking skills necessary for solving real-life problems.	3.21	0.85	Agreed
2	The teaching of Social Studies encourages students to analyze societal issues and propose effective solutions.	3.15	0.78	Agreed
3	Social Studies lessons enhance students' ability to evaluate multiple perspectives before making decisions.	2.89	0.92	Agreed
4	Through Social Studies, students acquire skills to evaluate my everyday experiences.	3.05	0.87	Agreed
5	Discussions and debates in Social Studies classes improve students' ability to think logically and solve problems.	3.12	0.81	Agreed
6	Social Studies education equips students with the necessary skills to resolve conflicts in their communities.	2.48	0.94	Disagreed
7	The problem-solving activities included in Social Studies curriculum prepare students for real-world challenges.	2.49	0.89	Disagreed
8	Social Studies education fosters creativity in students when addressing social and environmental problems.	3.08	0.86	Agreed

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Decision
9	The knowledge gained from Social Studies lessons helps students make informed decisions in challenging situations.	2.91	0.90	Agreed
10	Social Studies education provides students with the skills to assess causes and effects of societal issues critically.	2.78	0.88	Agreed
Cumulative Mean		2.92		Agreed

The cumulative mean score of **2.92** suggests that students generally agree that Social Studies education contributes to the development of critical thinking skills. However, the lower mean scores for conflict resolution and real-world problem-solving indicate areas that may require curriculum improvements. The standard deviations (ranging from 0.78 to 0.94) show moderate variation in responses, suggesting that while many students acknowledge the role of Social Studies in critical thinking, their experiences may differ depending on teaching methods and curriculum implementation. Thus, Social Studies education in upper basic schools in Delta State has a **moderate impact** on fostering critical thinking, particularly in logical reasoning, analysis of societal issues, and decision-making. However, enhancing the curriculum with more practical problem-solving and conflict-resolution activities could further strengthen its effectiveness.

Research question 3: What impact does Social Studies education have on the development of problem-solving skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State?

Table 3: Social Studies and development of problem-solving skills

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Decision
1	Social Studies classes encourage me to question assumptions and explore multiple perspectives on historical events.	3.21	0.69	Agreed
2	Through Social Studies, I have learned to evaluate the credibility of various information sources.	3.10	0.71	Agreed
3	The subject has enhanced my ability to identify bias and detect misinformation in media.	2.47	0.80	Disagreed
4	Social Studies assignments require me to analyze evidence before forming conclusions.	3.23	0.59	Agreed
5	Class discussions in Social Studies help me develop well-reasoned arguments.	3.35	0.68	Agreed

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Decision
6	I am encouraged to connect past events to current issues to foster deeper analytical thinking.	2.09	0.58	Disagreed
7	Social Studies projects have improved my problem-solving skills by addressing real-world challenges.	3.19	0.67	Agreed
Cumulative Mean		2.95		Agreed

The cumulative mean score of 2.95 suggests that students generally agree that Social Studies education supports the development of problem-solving skills. However, the results reveal inconsistencies in certain areas, particularly in helping students identify bias, detect misinformation, and connect past events to current issues. The standard deviations, ranging from 0.58 to 0.80, indicate moderate variation in responses, suggesting that while some students benefit significantly from Social Studies education, others may not experience its full impact due to differences in instructional methods.

Hypothesis 1: Social Studies education does not significantly enhance youth skills acquisition among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State.

Table 4: Chi-square Analysis on how Social Studies enhance youth skill acquisition among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

Variables	N	Df	Ls	Crit X ₂ value	Calc X ₂ value	Decision
Social Studies	250	2	0.05	5.991	46.500	Rejected
Youth skills acquisition						

Table 4 above showed that the calculated chi-square value of 46.500 is greater than the critical chi-square value of 5.991 at 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that Social Studies education does not significantly enhance youth skills acquisition among students in upper basic schools in Delta State is hereby rejected. This implies that Social Studies education significantly enhances youth skills acquisition among students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2: Social Studies education has no significant impact on the development of critical thinking among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

Table 5: Chi-square Analysis for the impact of Social Studies on the development of critical thinking skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

Variables	N	Df	Ls	Crit X ₂ value	Calc X ₂ value	Decision
Social Studies	250	2	0.05	5.991	151.907	Rejected
Problem solving skills						

Table 5 above showed that the calculated chi-square value of 151.907 is greater than the critical chi-square value of 5.991 at 0.05 significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that *Social Studies education has no significant impact on the development of critical thinking among students in upper basic schools in Delta State* is hereby rejected. This implies that Social Studies education has a significant impact on the development of critical thinking skills among students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Hypothesis 3: Social Studies education has no significant impact on the development of problem-solving skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

Table 6: Chi-square Analysis for the impact of Social Studies on the development of problem-solving skills among students in Upper Basic Schools in Delta State

Variables	N	Df	Ls	Crit X ₂ value	Calc X ₂ value	Decision
Social Studies	250	2	0.05	5.991	75.907	Rejected
Problem solving skills						

Table 6 above showed that the calculated chi-square value of 75.907 is greater than the critical chi-square value of **5.991** at **0.05** significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that *Social Studies education has no significant impact on the development of problem-solving skills among students in upper basic schools in Delta State* is hereby rejected. This implies that Social Studies education has a significant impact on the development of problem-solving skills among students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in table 1 revealed that students generally agreed that the Social Studies significantly contribute to the development of essential life skills. This finding corroborates the assertion of

Muhammad (2024), who maintains that Social Studies education is specifically designed to equip learners with the knowledge, skills, and values required for meaningful participation in society. It also aligns with the views of Achor et al. (2017), who emphasize that the Social Studies curriculum promotes entrepreneurship education and skill acquisition, particularly by creating awareness among adolescents about self-reliance and reducing youth unemployment. These scholarly views support the present study's result that Social Studies serves as a foundational tool for developing teamwork, communication, cultural competence, and community engagement skills among Upper Basic students in Delta State.

The results reveal that Social Studies education has a moderate impact on the development of critical thinking skills among students. Students agreed that Social Studies helps develop critical thinking and encourages the evaluation of multiple perspectives before making decisions. According to Obro et al. (2021) critical thinking involves the ability to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information effectively, which Social Studies aims to develop through its inquiry-based approach. Similarly, Bayram and Deveci (2022) emphasizes that Social Studies encourages students to explore historical and contemporary issues critically, leading to informed decision-making.

The findings from Table 3 indicate that Social Studies education contributes to the development of problem-solving skills among students. Students agreed that Social Studies assignments, projects, and discussions enhance their ability to evaluate evidence, form reasoned arguments, and analyze multiple perspectives. This aligns with the work of Ifegbesan (2023), who argues that Social Studies education should facilitate problem-solving by engaging students in inquiry-based learning. Similarly, Martinelle et al. (2024) asserts that problem-solving is central to education and should be cultivated through active learning experiences, which Social Studies provides.

Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the significant role of Social Studies education in enhancing youth skills acquisition in upper basic schools in Delta State. The study establishes that Social Studies contributes meaningfully to the development of essential life skills, including critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, which are crucial for students' academic and personal

growth. The results align with scholarly perspectives that emphasize the transformative power of Social Studies in equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary for effective participation in society. The study further confirms that Social Studies fosters an inquiry-based learning environment that promotes analytical thinking and decision-making, thereby preparing students for real-world challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Educational policymakers should strengthen the Social Studies curriculum to incorporate more skill-based learning activities that promote critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving.
2. Continuous professional development programs should be organized for Social Studies teachers to equip them with modern instructional strategies that enhance students' analytical and problem-solving skills.
3. Schools should integrate more inquiry-based learning methods, such as debates, case studies, and problem-solving projects, to deepen students' engagement with Social Studies content.
4. The government and school administrators should provide adequate teaching and learning resources, including digital tools, to facilitate interactive and engaging Social Studies lessons.
5. Regular assessment of students' critical thinking and problem-solving abilities should be conducted to measure the effectiveness of Social Studies education and identify areas for improvement.

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